

Monetary and Non Monetary Incentives in LIC of India and Its Impact in Salem City

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to secure the impact of monetary and non-monetary incentives on agents in LIC of India, Salem. To indicate the difference in employee attitudes related to job satisfaction and incentives on some demographical variables. The results of the study stated that extra pay, bonuses. The results determined a significant effect of both monetary and non-monetary incentives for better job performance, and incentive pay had a concrete linkage with satisfaction, performance, and motivation.

Keywords: Monetary incentives, Work performance, Job satisfaction, Job motivation

Introduction

The success and failure of a business are very much dependent on the performance of its employees or in other words, the appearance of the human resource of the enterprise. Several factors are supposed to influence the performance of the employees. Of course, the incentives, whether monetary or non-monetary differently, are a direct motivation to the employees to make to the greatest of their capacity. It presents a spur or zeal in the employees for better performance. Inspiration is something that motivates an individual to act. Therefore a hope for recompense is powerful to encourage employees to perform better. Motivated employees are also satisfied employees which helps them to play more efficiently and achieve the organizational goal. One of the many methods used to increase the motivation of employees is the incentive application. Incentives are commonly developed, toate employee motivation, satisfaction, and higher performance. The link between the three variables has been broadly considered and debated among researchers, scholars, and practitioners. They argue that the effectiveness of excuses for giving higher behavioral issues of employees is based on the extent to which those incentives are seen to satisfy or fulfill their needs.

It is widespread at such premises that there are often monetary and non-monetary incentive applications to award the employees with a high-performance level and to encourage the ones with lower performance levels for higher performance. The primary purpose

of such forms is to establish a fair management structure within the premise to contribute to the motivations of representatives as a social being and therefore to improve their productivity and efficiency by enhancing their job satisfaction levels. Nowadays, in the working sector with the advent of globalization, the use of incentives by the employer’s plays a fundamental role in workers satisfaction or the company’s effectiveness. How the employers treat their employees is the most significant asset; therefore, to encourage or to motivate workers is the critical component of every organization. All the incentives both tangible or intangible is motivating or became the reference for job satisfaction; as they help in changing the behavior of workers. With the rise in the organization’s competition, it is required that workers should deal with every aspect of their job with creativity and motivation, which help in managing the organization goals and perspectives. So to increase the level of interest in work, both monetary and non-monetary incentives are needed that is associated with work satisfaction among employees.

The theories of job motivation exist and shed some light on employee motivation; they all have any limitations, and thus, our understanding and knowledge of what motivates employees are still very much incomplete. Therefore, understanding what motivates employees to work near or at the highest level is a critical issue for all organizations. It is believed that an employee’s behaviorist influenced by the different types of incentives. Therefore, to reward as well as recognize more excellent performance, incentives are the critical tool regarding employee motivation.

Literature Review

A large number of studies have identified the effect of monetary and nonmonetary incentives on employee productivity and overall business performance. Numerous studies have more demonstrated that rewarding employees is one of the best ways to keep the workforce motivated. It has been found that how employee motivation is linked with incentives and recognition is strategically essential for achieving successful performance in an organization.

Al-Nsour (2012) examined the effects of financial and non-financial incentives at Jordanian university in terms of organizational performance. A significant relation was observed between financial and non-financial incentives and organizational performance by the data obtained from this study. Moreover, the study showed that financial incentives were highly regarded than non-financial incentives.

Ali Erbaş and Tugay Arat (2012) examined the effect of financial and non-financial incentives on job satisfaction and observed that the responsiveness to financial incentives was found to be lower than to non-financial incentives.

Saqib and M Akbar (2015) suggested that the balance between financial and non-financial rewards plays a role in increasing the level of job satisfaction, motivation and organizational commitment is a proposition which is generally accepted without argument.

Al-Angari (1999) examined the effects of incentive applications on the performances of employees and emphasized in the study that positive financial incentives do not satisfy the employees.

The Objective of the Study

- To analyze the impact of monetary and non-monetary incentives on LIC agents.
- To observe the impact of monetary and non-monetary rewards on Job Satisfaction.
- To identify different incentives provided to LIC agents.

Limitations of the Study

- The researchers could include only the position of LIC of India.
- The study does not contain the estimate of one private or public companies underinsurance industry in India.
- The area of the study is retained limited due to the quick time and financial position.

LIC of India

Life Insurance Corporation of India was an Indian State-owned insurance group, and investment company headquartered in Mumbai. It is the highest insurance company in India with an estimated asset value of 1,560,482 crores (US\$230 billion). As of 2013 it had total life fund of Rs.1433103.14 crore with a total amount of policies sold of 367.82 lakh that year. The Life Insurance Corporation of India was founded in 1956 when the Parliament of India established the Life Insurance of India Act that nationalized the private insurance industry in India. Over 245 Insurance companies and provident societies were merged to create the state-owned Life Insurance Corporation. Even after 16 years of competition (the insurance sector was opened to private firms in 2000), LIC still enjoys over 76.99 percent of the market pie in terms of inclusive policies. The largest financial institution with over Rs 22.10 lakh crore in assets which is over 15 percent of India's GDP of Rs 134 lakh crore.

Concept of Monetary and Non-Monetary Incentives

Financial incentive enhance the direct satisfaction of employees, and the non-monetary motivation is helpful for the recognition of employees, and that recognition is a motivational tool for the employees and leads to an increase in performance. Monetary incentives can boost motivation, but non-monetary incentives are more efficient motivators because these incentives have an intrinsic motivational impact on the workers. So, intrinsically motivated workers naturally enjoy their work or job. Commercial incentives are developed to satisfy essential human needs, encouraging and pushing people to do their best work performance, the recruitment of their capabilities and improve their competencies level. Monetary incentives are also produced as a means of payment to increase productivity and improve employee work performance. Therefore, the more employees provide, the more they can get.

Although monetary incentives are the key to developing employees' motivation, work satisfaction, and better performance, several non-monetary incentives may represent more effective means of enhancing the quality of work product as well as motivational level. Also, non-monetary incentives can promote staff loyalty, enhance more interaction and cooperation among subordinates and superiors, enable more possibility for staff participation or involvement, and so on. Non-monetary incentives could be in the form of issuing a certificate of thanks and appreciation, providing extra training courses as a part of capacity developing programs, or organizing parties for distinguished staff. Non-monetary incentives are sometimes known as moral incentives, which is concerned with various aspects of psychological needs, and the increasing concentration of these aspects come after the emergence of related human theories (Akaili, 1996). Moral incentives mostly based on the respect of a human being who has an hopes, aspiration, and emotional feeling.

Monetary Incentive in LIC

Giving of bonus: It is an extra payment over and above salary, and it acts as an incentive for hard work. Knowing there is a substantial financial reward for increased productivity can make precisely the kind of motivation to many agents. A competition which was there in April 2017 in which if the agents procure Rs 50000 as New Policy Instalment then the agent would be suitable to get a bonus of Rs 400. In July if the agents can obtain four policies in the given time frame, then the agents are qualified to get Rs 700 as a bonus.

Travel Allowance: It is the more benefit which is given to the agents. It acts as a monetary incentive; it requires financial tangibility in it. LIC also provides travel allowance, which acts as a tool for moving the employees to continuous increase their performance. And it is performed according to the various club from which the agent belongs. In which the corporate understands the maximum, i.e., 2,00,000 annually.

Nonmonetary Incentives

Training: Agents are given regular exercise to enrich them; it becomes the personality of the agents, which in turn satisfies them, which may start to motivate the agents to prove themselves. The training program adopted in LIC is excellent. The top-level management plays an active role in implementing training programs. The agents were distributed a target to be achieved, and the qualifying agents are provided to attend a motivational cum educational seminar by a renowned speaker.

Praise or recognition: Recognition or Praise is another incentive which satisfies the ego of the agents. Sometimes compliments become more effective than any other tool. LIC agents are consistently accepted and rewarded for their execution. Numerous competitions all year round increase healthy competition amongst agents and appreciation for their efforts.

Gifts: The agents are given various types of gifts items such as umbrella, rain jacket wall clocks as a promotional giveaway item to motivate the agents for an excellent performance. The amount or the value of the gift depends upon the level in which the agents belong to.

Mediclaime Facility: It has also become important in everyone life as all are bothered about their own and their family’s health and well-being. LIC gives its agents the group mediclaime, which differs the amount of claim according to their membership. The Branch Members get the least of one lakh, and the corporate understands the maximum, i.e., five lakhs.

Overview of Work Motivation

The competition among organizations and businesses is making it more challenging to achieve their goal. Work motivation is a primary factor for progression within an organization and company. According to circumstances, one of the most effective strategies for achieving organizational or business goals is work motivation. The way organizations motivate their employees can affect on how employees perceive their working environment and culture within their organization. Most workers who are motivated produce a higher quality of work product as well as work effectiveness. And motivation refers to “the psychological method that gives behavior purpose and direction, a predisposition to behave in a purposive manner to perform specific unmet needs, an unsatisfied need, and the will to achieve, respectively.” Since the primary purpose of incentive is to promote and increase employee motivation, some of these three variables should be taken into account. The first is individual characteristics, the second variable is job characteristics, which contains some variables such as rewards, level of work autonomy, duty, responsibility and so on and the third variable concerns the attributes of the work-related environment.

The Effect of Motivation on Work Satisfaction

Research seeking to find better methods of motivating people in the workplace has made some researchers and scholars to further reduce on the psychological factors that can stimulate work satisfaction among employees. The greatest potential motivators are the things that employees overwhelmingly desire and value. The motivation that leads to job satisfaction is assoc.

They are rated with the nature of the work itself. Herzberg has included job-related practices, such as job recognition, the praise of employee’s achievement. Motivation can be extrinsic or intrinsic. Sometimes people act not because they are intrinsically motivated, but fairly because outside factors prompt them to take action. Accordingly, regardless of financial, physical, or emotional circumstances, outcomes are still the primary motivator of job performance. It is possible that the organization can improve their productivities, or gain competitive advantage through productive, qualified, and motivated employees. The primary determinant of work satisfaction is job intrinsic, which is generally called motivation; this includes job responsibility, the opportunity

for improvement, work recognition, and so on. Also, an individual's level of satisfaction with his/her work can reflect the degree to which he/she values their role either implicitly or explicitly as it allows or fulfills the fulfillment of their job value.

The linkage between incentives, role satisfaction, and work performance.

The active organizations make effective use of people knowledge and skills, which commonly occur when people align their proper intentions with that of the establishment they work for. Meanwhile, job-related characteristics and overall working environment are also crucial in the context of job satisfaction. In extension to this, the degree of self-satisfaction felt by people or groups of people in the workplace can arrange their overall performance, which suggests satisfaction positively affects work performance. This suggestion has theoretical roots, but it also indicates the common belief among scholars that "a happy worker is a productive worker." Therefore, when the difficulty of performance exists, it is far extra advantageous to deal with or to improve workers' satisfaction than to deal direct with their performance. From this aspect, the overall work performance of an organization is much dependent on the productivity of individuals or groups within the organization. Therefore, to attract, motivate and retain excellent performance and very productive staff and to be fair to all employees, an organization requires to set up and acquire incentive schemes to reward and recognize employees' performance based on their relative productivity.

Hypothesis: The two significant hypotheses tested and analyzed in this study are

H0: There is no impact on providing incentives to the agents.

H1: There is a significant impact on presenting incentives to agents.

Research Methodology

This study has a representative scanning model, which aims to indicate the variation in terms of any demographical characteristics on the attitudes of employees related to incentives and job satisfaction, also to examine the impact of monetary and nonmonetary incentives applied at LIC in on motivation and job satisfaction. In the study, field research is used to test these hypotheses. This research was based on the primary data collected through a detailed questionnaire containing 15 questions. The first part of the inquiry relating to the socio-economic background of the respondents consisted of 6 issues relating to name, age, income, educational qualification, etc. The second part of the application consisted of 9 questions about several factors of avenue selection for the study. In this study, it will be considered that employees with high satisfaction, motivation, and recognition regularly perform well. The sample size was 30, and the respondents obtained randomly selected from that urban investor of Salem district of Jharkhand. The means of gathering primary data is mainly based on qualitative interviews. Qualitative interviews give an extra dimension, which allows the researcher to explore the research questions from a various angle. This technique is useful, mainly when the research aims to develop depth and further understanding. The primary data obtained from the questionnaire were analyzed.

The primary device used for this research was the face-to-face interview. The interview inquiries were created based on an extensive review of distributed academic literature concerning the research topic. The researcher conveyed interview questions that were semi-structured to allow the interviewees to express their ideas or opinions instead of just answering the questions. This technique gave more in-depth information about their perception toward the incentive system within as well as their expectation to the entire organization. A qualitative interview is often called semi-structured for the questions are well established, but with some possibilities for the participants to expose their thoughts, feedback, and manage the direction of the interview.

Analysis & Discussion

The qualitative data were separated using thematic analysis as qualitative analysis procedures. According to King (2004b), thematic analysis introduces the description of core themes and sub-themes in qualitative data. The text from open-ended interview questions is analyzed using a coding procedure and reduced into a set of critical issues and sub-themes through the entire method of data analysis. For this research study, thematic analysis of interview transcripts was performed to highlight common themes of the research. First, reading carefully for the entire transcripts. Second, each presented response from the interview was divided into smaller, meaningful pieces of information. Then the researcher had considered that information in further detail to figure out the key variables that developed from the participants’ responses. This system was highlighted and underlined for the next step. Last, those labeled and highlighted points were grouped, and the so coded chunks of coded text were put collectively to form categories, core themes, and sub-themes. This process provided the researcher to identify various variables, which merged from the transcribed data and classified them into particular groups.

Conclusion

Based on the literature review and research findings, we can say that an appropriate incentive system supports employees to perform their best performance. Work performance as the importance of job satisfaction and job satisfaction can be obtained from different incentives as employee motivation. The result obtained from this study shows significant similarity to the reviewed literature. Even though any were not what we expected, those exceptions established a small percentage in the research findings, which can be shaded light for a future research study. The results showed a meaningful effect of both monetary and nonmonetary incentives for better job performance. The selected participants displayed different job dissatisfaction toward the non-availability of several reasons, which significantly affected their overall work production. The majority of the interviewees described that they are happy with their goals for their appearance. Two respondents did say, however, that though he was not provided, it didn’t affect his performance. The meeting resulted as the majority of interviewees get motivated with both the incentives monetary and non-monetary. In general, the results showed that providing further financial and nonmonetary incentives to public employees could improve their work performance and increase productivity.

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